

THE ANALYSIS OF FERTILIZER FILTER, WHICH INCREASES THE PURITY QUALITY OF THE WORKING FLUID IN THE HYDRAULIC SYSTEM

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Annotation

Hydraulic excavators used in the mining and construction industries today require an in-depth study of the working fluid cleaning of the working fluid from the porous filter. The working fluid of the excavator is important to ensure the efficient operation of hydraulic excavators. This article provides a detailed comparison and analysis of layered and non-layered methods of working fluid thinking of hydraulic excavators in operation around the world. In order to ensure the cleanliness of the working fluid of hydraulic excavators used in the country, work has been done to localize the filters to see the economic benefits of achieving the above results

The resulting porous material is sampled under a microscope using a Digital Microscope Model: x4 with a 640x480 extension (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Digital Microscope model of porous material: samples taken at x4.

The coordinate line of the micrometer calibration line (Figure 3) is photographed under a microscope (Digital Microscope model: x4) with a resolution of 640x480, and the dimensions of the pores are taken from each of the samples using an LED copy panel with a coordinate calibration line. Figure 4)

Figure 3. Micrometer calibration line and coordinate line.

a)

b)

1-sample

2-sample

d)

Figure 4. The method of determining the pore size of the porous filter: a-LED copying panel, b-pore detection process, d-pore sizing samples.

In the next step of our experiment, we will consider the cleaning of the working fluid from the porous filter, which operated 3970 and 3088 motor hours on a hydraulic excavator RH-40E brand brands tellus46 and tellus 68.

Cleaning was performed in 2 ways.

1st layer.

Without 2 layers.

1 method.

The porous filter is cut into slices and stacked on top of the dish (Fig. 5). The working fluid is filtered under atmospheric pressure for 2 hours.

Figure 5 Layered cleaning of hydraulic working fluid with porous filter.

Method 2

The porous filter is made in the form of a vessel and the working fluid is filtered (Fig. 6). The working fluid is filtered under atmospheric pressure for 4 hours.

Figure 6 Layerless cleaning of hydraulic working fluids in a porous filter. In both methods, samples of filtered working fluids are taken. (Figure 7)

Tellus 46
working fluid in
the initial state

Tellus 46
3790 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E Working
fluid

Tellus 46
3790 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E is a working
fluid filtered by
method 1

Tellus 46
3790 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E is a working
fluid filtered by
method 2

Tellus 68
working fluid in
the initial state

Tellus 68
3088 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E Working
fluid

Tellus 68
3088 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E is a working
fluid filtered by
method 1

Tellus 68
3088 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E is a working
fluid filtered by
method 2

Figure 7. Filtered samples of hydraulic working fluid in a porous medium
The samples are examined under a microscope (model) at a magnification
of 1000 times to check for filtered differences. (Figure 8)

Tellus 46
the structure of
the working fluid
in the initial
state.

Tellus 46
3790 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E Working
working fluid
structure.

Tellus 46
3790 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E Structure of
working fluid
filtered by
method 1.

Tellus 46
3790 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E Structure of
working fluid
filtered by
method 2.

Tellus 68
the structure of
the working fluid
in the initial
state.

Tellus 68
3088 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E Working
working fluid
structure.

Tellus 68
3088 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E Structure of
working fluid
filtered by
method 1.

Tellus 68
3088 moto /
hour
Hydraulic
excavator RH-
40E Structure of
working fluid
filtered by
method 2.

Figure 8. Microscopic view of filtered states of hydraulic working fluid.

Conclusion

This means that the hydraulic excavator is not sufficiently equipped with layered and non-layered methods to clean the working fluid from the porous filter, which adversely affects the efficiency of the supply of spare parts. Therefore, cleaning of the hydraulic excavator working fluid from the porous filter requires consideration of measures to localize the supply.

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